

SUPERHYDROPHOBIC SURFACES AND NANOTECHNOLOGY: A BRIEF REVIEW**Mehejbin R. Mujawar**

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Corresponding author E-mail: mehejabeenmujawar@gmail.com**ABSTRACT**

Recently, the Lotus leaf-inspired superhydrophobic coating has been used in various industrial applications. Among them, the use of superhydrophobic materials for potential application prospects such as oil-water separation has gained growing interest. However, a simple and low-cost strategy for the fabrication of durable superhydrophobic materials remains a major challenge. The separation of the oil-water mixture is one of the most important applications of superhydrophobic coating. Herein, the superhydrophobic coated stainless steel mesh can be separated easily oil from the oil-water mixture. The candle soot has the advantages of cost-effectiveness and production scalability over other carbons (i.e. graphene, carbon nano-tubes, etc.) in the synthesis. The superhydrophobic coated mesh can be separated easily oil from the oil-water mixture. The present work describes the facile fabrication method of preparation of superhydrophobic stainless steel mesh. The layer of candle soot particles is deposited on the mesh by holding in the middle part of a candle flame and thereafter wax is deposited using the dip-coating method to form the candle soot-wax composite coating. The water contact angle was 155° and the oil contact angle of nearly 0° reveals the formation of superhydrophobic stainless steel mesh that efficiently separates the oil-water mixture. So, this superhydrophobic mesh can be applicable to use in industries for oil-water separation.

Keywords:

Candle Soot, Superhydrophobic Surface, Oil-Water Separation, Water Contact Angle, Nanotechnology, Nanomaterials.

INTRODUCTION

Superhydrophobicity is an attribute of around 200 plants and insects that nature has generated. Superhydrophobic surfaces have proven to be an economical and environmentally beneficial option. A superhydrophobic surface has a sliding angle of less than 10° and a water contact angle (WCA) greater than 150° . Superhydrophobic surfaces are extremely water-repellent when they aren't wet. Numerous flora and insects exist, including rice leaves, lotus leaves, gecko feet, rose petals, strider legs, mosquito eyes, butterfly wings, and many more [1]. A well-known symbol for superhydrophobicity is the lotus leaf. They are superhydrophobic, which helps them stay clean despite living in a muddy environment. A homogeneous layer of micro-nanostructures and epicuticular wax crystalloids covers the surface of a lotus leaf [2].

*Fig. 1. Superhydrophobic Surfaces***1. Smart Coating:**

The synthesis of nanotechnology and nanomaterials has led to many breakthroughs in the coatings business. Smart coatings can respond to outside influences and adjust to environmental changes. The upcoming generation of

sophisticated coatings, known as "smart coatings," reacts to environmental changes, including variations in temperature, mechanical induction, pressure, ion exchange, heat, light irradiation, wettability, and aggressive corrosion. Other names for smart coatings include environmentally sensitive coatings, intelligent coatings, and stimuli-responsive coatings [3–6]. The passive properties of smart coatings, such as their anti-inflammatory, anti-corrosion, pH-responsive, self-cleaning, anti-icing, and anti-microbial properties, make them useful. Oil-water separation and self-healing coatings [7–11].

Fig. 2. Smart coatings and their types

The enhanced qualities of smart coatings, like their transparency, ductility, scratch resistance, chemical and mechanical capabilities, etc., have created a demand for them. Applications for smart coatings in the textile, medical, construction, transportation, electronics, and many other industries are growing [12]. Smart coatings are classified according to several variables, including applications, functions, responsiveness, material kinds, degrees of complexity, and manufacturing methods for functional constitutions [13–14]. The focus of this field's research has shifted to meet demands for superhydrophobic coatings that can mend themselves and clean themselves, among other things [15].

2. Nanoscience and Nanotechnology:

The Greek word "nano" means "dwarf" or "very small," and it represents one thousand millionths of a meter (10⁻⁹ m). Nanotechnology uses structures and chemicals at scales of nanometers to 100 nm in practical applications, such as devices. The study of these kinds of molecules and structures is known as nanoscience [16].

3. Nanoscience:

The origins of nanoscience can be found in the 5th century B.C., during the time of Democritus and the Greeks. At that time, Scientists were discussing whether matter is continuous and ultimately constantly divided into smaller pieces, or if it is made up of tiny, indivisible, and indestructible particles called atoms [17]. Physics, materials science, and biology come together in nanoscience to study the manipulation of materials at the atomic and molecular levels.

Fig. 3. Applications of Nanoscience and Nanotechnology

4. Nanotechnology:

Nanotechnology is among the most fascinating emerging technologies of the 21st century. It is the capacity to synthesize, assemble, control, and construct matter at the nanoscale through observation, measurement, and manipulation to apply the theory of nanoscience to practical situations. Nanotechnology is the term for technology applied to the nanoscale, where materials, systems, or devices are created by manipulating matter at the nanoscale to enhance the specific characteristics of the material at the nanoscale [18].

5. Properties of nanomaterials:

Numerous applications can benefit from the unique qualities of nanomaterials, which include their huge surface area, optical activity, mechanical strength, and chemical reactivity.

Fig. 4. Properties of Nanomaterials

6. Structural Properties:

It is noted that a material's properties undergo significant changes when it approaches the nanoscale. Because of precipitation in suspension solutions, it can occasionally be difficult to determine the surface-active properties of nanomaterials. Because of the intricate process involved in creating nanoparticles, significant effort is needed for this kind of preparation [19]. Three layers may be distinguished in the nanomaterial. These materials are the surface, shell, and core. The qualities of nanomaterials and their essential components for every application are reflected in the core material. The development of nanomaterials along different crystallographic directions determines their crystalline forms and planar layouts. Thus, crystalline solids have distinct patterns and long-range periodic atom configurations [20].

7. Optical Properties:

The size and surface plasmon resonance of nanomaterials, as determined by various spectroscopic methods, are considered their optical properties. The energy of electronic states, such as the highly inhibited valence band and other lower unoccupied molecular orbits like the conduction band, determines the optical properties [21]. When electronic transitions between these states cause absorption and emission, an optical quality is seen. Because it may be altered in many ways, including size, nature, doping, and surface functionalization, this property has been demonstrated.

8. Thermal Properties:

Since nanoparticles are very different from bulk materials in terms of size, shape, and surface area, there are many ways to alter their thermal characteristics. Thermal properties can be evaluated as the response to thermal energy transmitted by phonons that occur throughout a broad frequency spectrum. Thus, nanomaterials use phonon wavelengths and mean-free paths. A change in transmission quantization and phonon captivity automatically results in a change in the thermal property [22].

9. Superhydrophobic Surfaces:

Superhydrophobic surfaces are very desirable for their numerous applications because of their unique nano- and micro-scale roughness and low surface energy, which provide them with exceptional water-repellency qualities. When a

surface has a low sliding angle of less than 5° and a high contact angle of more than 150° , it is generally regarded as superhydrophobic. Superhydrophobic surfaces are frequently seen on plant leaves and insect wings in the natural world. A well-known symbol of superhydrophobicity, lotus leaves are also recognized for their polyurethanerity due to their inherent capacity for self-cleaning. Due to the low surface energy of the outermost molecular layer, which is made up of wax crystals, the leaf's surface roughness on both a nano- and micro-scale has been linked to the root cause of its superhydrophobicity [23–24].

10. Natural Superhydrophobic Surfaces:

Surface micro- and nanostructures and low-surface-energy chemical compounds are fundamental requirements for high water repellency, as demonstrated by a surface study of natural superhydrophobic surfaces. The Wenzel [25] Cassie-Baxter [26] model states that optimizing and raising the surface roughness value will improve hydrophobicity. Water droplets on a Wenzel-type rough surface pierce the structure, but they lock over it to maintain a high contact angle. Researchers are focusing on developing artificial superhydrophobic surfaces by emulating physical and chemical processes after being drawn to natural superhydrophobic surfaces [27–28].

Table 1: Superhydrophobic surfaces present in nature

Natural Surface	Water Contact Angle	Property
Rice leaf	164°	Superhydrophobic
Rose petal	154.6°	Superhydrophobic
Mosquito eyes	155°	Superhydrophobic
Desert beetle	$>150^\circ$	Superhydrophobic
Butterfly wings	152°	Superhydrophobic
Sharkskin	160°	Superhydrophobic
Gecko foot	150°	Superhydrophobic
Indian cress	180°	Superhydrophobic
Water strider legs	168°	Superhydrophobic
Lotus leaf	$>150^\circ$	Superhydrophobic

11. Basic Wetting Phenomenon:

Due to intermolecular interactions, wetting is the capacity of a liquid to stay in touch with a strong surface when they are brought together. Force stability between cohesive and adhesive forces determines the degree of wetness. Three material stages are available for wetting: gas, liquid, and solid. Wet phenomena are common in both technology and the natural world. Wetting phenomena represent a field where engineering, physics, and chemistry come together. The term "surface" refers to a two-dimensional plane that divides two phases macroscopically. However, even in tiny microcosms, a third dimension exists. The thickness of this interfacial layer varies from a few nanometres to interatomic distances [29–30]. In actuality, we will always be addressing the characteristics at the interface between the two phases while addressing all of the surfaces' physical and chemical characteristics. Generally speaking, modifications to any of the two stages involved can have an impact on an interface's characteristics. Regarding the three states of matter, there are five conceivable interfaces: gas-liquid, gas-solid, liquid-liquid, liquid-solid, and solid-solid. When it comes to two substances adhering or bonding, wetting is essential. Certain related outcomes, such as capillary consequences, are also attributable

to wetting and the surface forces that regulate wetting. The surface tension of the droplet and the surface energy of the platform play major roles in the wetting of a droplet on a surface. On a level surface, a droplet can take on the shape of a cap. Surface tension is the phenomenon responsible for the liquid droplet's creation of its spherical shape. The liquid will soak the solid surface if the liquid's attraction to it is greater than the liquid molecules' intermolecular attraction. Conversely, if the liquid molecules' intermolecular attraction is stronger than the attraction between liquid and solid, it will be harder to wet the solid surface [31-32].

Fig. 5. A schematic showing (a) a hydrophilic surface with a water contact angle less than 90° ; (b) a hydrophobic surface with a water contact angle greater than 90° and (c) a superhydrophobic surface with a water contact angle larger than 150° .

Spreading a liquid over a solid surface is necessary for many practical procedures, particularly those involving paints and lubricants. On the other side, solid surfaces' non-wetting characteristics are crucial for various operations, such as rust prevention. If a liquid is wettable by a solid, the liquid will tend to be drawn into the pores of the porous solid body. Water must also enter the porous rock channels that were primarily filled with oil during the tertiary oil recovery phase. As a result, research on solid-liquid interfaces has been ongoing for a long time. Adhesion, printing, cleaning, painting, lubricating, and many other common activities in daily life, biology, and industry are examples of wetting-dependent processes. As such, there has been a lot of interest in characterizing the wettability of solid surfaces. By storing a fluid drop at first glance and measuring the contact angle, it is possible to approximate the wetting behavior of a fluid on a solid surface (Figure 2). A solid surface is generally measured as hydrophilic when the contact angle is less than 90° and as hydrophobic when the contact angle is more than 90° .

Fig. 6. Contact angle of a water drop on a solid surface, (a) hydrophilic, and (b) hydrophobic

There is energy connected to any interface because atoms on the surface have more power than those in the bulk. Liquid tends to flow across an exposed solid surface when the specific energy (J/m^2) of the solid-vapor interface, γ_{sv} , is greater than that of the solid-liquid interface, γ_{sl} . Upon contact between a small liquid droplet and a flat solid surface, three separate equilibrium areas can be identified, as depicted in Figure 7: partial wetting [Figures 7(a) and 3(b)] with a finite contact angle θ ; entire wetting [figures 7(c) and 7(d)], with $\theta = 180^\circ$ for complete non-wetting [33]. When there is partial wetting, a certain "contact line" determines the area of the wet surface. There are two interfaces for a liquid layer on a flat solid surface [Figure 7(c)]: liquid-vapor (γ_{lv}) and solid-liquid (γ_{sl}).

Fig. 7. A water droplet in equilibrium over a horizontal solid surface

12. Young's Equation:

The border separating the three phases that are in contact is referred to as a contact line. A typical illustration of contact between three phases—water, glass, and air—is a drop of water on a piece of glass. The "contact line" is the water droplet's rim where it touches the glass. Three interfaces can be seen in such a system: solid-liquid, liquid-vapor, and solid-vapor. The solid surface characteristic of the three-phase system is found to be at an angle with the tangent to the liquid-vapor interface drawn at the contact line. For this reason, the angle is regarded as a thermodynamic feature. We refer to it as the "contact angle." Young's equation, first presented by Thomas Young in 1805, served as the foundation for the science of wettability [34]. Young's equation can be used to find the contact angle for a droplet placed on an ideal surface (figure 4), which is an isotropic, chemically homogeneous, non-reactive, and non-deformed atomically flat solid surface.

$$\cos \theta = \frac{(\gamma_{sv} - \gamma_{sl})}{\gamma_{lv}} \quad (I)$$

The equilibrium contact angle, also known as Young's contact angle, is denoted by θ , and the surface tensions of the liquid-vapor, solid-liquid, and solid-vapor are represented by γ_{lv} , γ_{sl} , and γ_{sv} , respectively. According to Young's equation, a droplet on the previously described surface will inevitably gravitate toward the lowest energy with a balanced state, and the interaction between the three interfaces establishes the equilibrium contact angle. In the fully wet state, where $\gamma_{sv} > \gamma_{sl} + \gamma_{lv}$, force balance is impossible. As for the non-wetting case, $0 < \cos \theta < 0$, and the partial wetting case, $0 < \cos \theta < 1$ [35]. It can be inferred from the experimentally recorded equilibrium water contact angle (WCA) whether the surface is hydrophobic (hating water) or hydrophilic (loving water). A surface is considered hydrophilic if a water droplet forms a contact angle of less than 90° on it. A surface is classified as hydrophobic if its WCA is greater than 90° but less than 150° , and as superhydrophobic if its WCA is greater than 150° . WCA $\sim 0^\circ$ indicates complete wetting, which happens for liquids with very low surface tension or a surface with high surface energy [36]. For hydrophobic surfaces, the opposite is true; for hydrophilic surfaces, $\gamma_{sl} < \gamma_{sv}$. It should be noted, nevertheless, that there is disagreement about whether the substrate represents the hydrophilic-hydrophobic boundary at WCA= 90° . Berg et al. proposed that the hydrophilic-hydrophobic boundary is located at around 65° based on the attraction-repulsion forces of chemistry [37].

Fig. 8. A schematic representation of Young's wetting model

Due to the liquid surface involved in both γ_{SL} and γ_{LV} , a tension, σ_S , must exist on the left side of equation (I) to balance the two tangential capillary tensions, γ_{SL} and $\gamma_{LV} \cos \theta$. But as was previously mentioned, capillarity on an unrestrained solid surface (as γ_{SV} in Young's construction) does not give rise to σ_S . The force that pulls the contact line away from the liquid side is just the system's counterforce to the total of its two capillary tensions. Figure 5 illustrates this. Since a solid surface is formed, creating an additional opposing tension γ_{SV} , transferring the contact line to the liquid side necessitates external labor, which is why it is pinned [38].

Fig. 9. Tension vectors at the three-phase line.

Young's model offers a mathematically simplified explanation of surface wettability; nonetheless, it frequently falls short of describing the wettability of a surface with surface heterogeneity and roughness. Surface roughness or heterogeneities are significant in the real-world environment. Two more distinct models—the Wenzel and Cassie-Baxter models—also theoretically consider the impact of macroscopic roughness on wettability [39].

Fig. 10. A schematic shows a water droplet's behavior on a rough surface in (a) Wenzel's and (b) Cassie-Baxter's state.

CONCLUSION

Superhydrophobic surfaces, inspired by natural phenomena such as the lotus leaf effect, have revolutionized various industries through their ability to repel water and resist contamination. These surfaces, engineered using

nanotechnology, offer remarkable properties, including self-cleaning, anti-corrosion, anti-icing, and drag reduction. Advancements in nanotechnology have enabled the precise design and fabrication of nanostructures that enhance superhydrophobicity. Superhydrophobic materials that last and work well have been made possible by methods like chemical vapor deposition, electrospinning, and nanocomposite coatings. These innovations have promising applications in fields ranging from biomedical devices and textiles to aerospace and marine industries. Despite their advantages, challenges such as long-term durability, scalability, and environmental concerns regarding nanomaterials remain. Future research must focus on enhancing the mechanical robustness of superhydrophobic surfaces, improving their cost-effectiveness, and ensuring their eco-friendliness.

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